

Exploring the Carbon Footprint's Effect on Life Cycle Costs with Digitalization's Support

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Abstract

This study addresses the integration of life cycle cost (LCC) analysis with the carbon footprint of assets, emphasizing the importance of environmental sustainability in decision-making. A formula is proposed to incorporate carbon emissions costs into traditional LCC analysis, providing a comprehensive view of the total costs of an asset. A step-by-step digitalization approach is proposed, involving asset identification, data monitoring, LCC calculation, carbon footprint costing, cost integration, and identification of optimization opportunities. The Digital Twin concept is introduced for tracking the carbon footprint at the asset level. The document underlines the benefits of digitalization, such as increased data accuracy, real-time monitoring, predictive analytics, optimized reporting, lifecycle optimization, support for circular economy principles, and stakeholder engagement. Digitalization can be seen as a tool for monitoring and reporting and also for achieving substantial changes that affect the environment. The critical role of effective asset management and maintenance in reducing the carbon footprint in organizations is highlighted, with digitalization emerging as an enabler for better decision-making toward environmental and financial sustainability.

Keywords: Asset management; Maintenance; Carbon footprint; Digitalization; Environmental sustainability; Greenhouse gas emissions

1. Introduction and background

The world is undergoing two simultaneous transitions: ecological and digital. The ecological transition aims, among other goals, to promote a circular economy by improving production processes, reducing greenhouse gas emissions, and using recycled materials throughout the product lifecycle. Addressing the climate crisis is crucial and requires reducing greenhouse gas emissions; however, the world's population is growing, particularly in Asian countries such as India and China, which are also the largest emitters of greenhouse gas emissions because they need more energy to grow economically than the more developed countries (Ortega et al., 2022; Mena et al., 2023). Meanwhile, the digital transition seeks to enhance our infrastructure and technologies, empowering us to create a more digital economy and society by digitizing the entire value chain across critical sectors. These transitions offer a remarkable opportunity to decarbonize our economies and achieve sustainable economic growth, supported by digital technologies and data management techniques (Sharma et al., 2022; Spaltini et al., 2024). Although this study only considers the carbon footprint as a driver of climate change, in reality, there may be other factors within companies that have an impact (Table 2).

Table 1. Drivers of Climate Change

Impact Category	Description
1. Climate Change (also known as Global Warming)	A measure of greenhouse gas emissions, such as CO ₂ and methane. These emissions cause an increase in Earth's radiation absorption. They lead to adverse effects on ecosystem health, human health, and material well-being.
2. Eutrophication (also known as Overfertilization)	Encompasses the potential impacts of excessively high levels of macronutrients, including nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P). Nutrient enrichment can lead to undesirable changes in species composition and elevated biomass production in aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems, causing issues like toxic algae blooms.

3. Acidification	A measure of emissions causing acidifying effects on the environment. Acidification potential quantifies a molecule's ability to increase hydrogen ion (H ⁺) concentration, leading to decreased pH values, for example, acid rain. Potential effects include fish mortality, forest decline, and deterioration of construction materials.
4. Smog Formation (also known as Photochemical Ozone Creation)	A measure of emissions of precursors contributing to ground-level smog (mainly ozone O ₃) produced by the reaction of VOC and carbon monoxide in the presence of nitrogen oxides under UV light. Ground-level ozone can be harmful to human health, ecosystems, and crops.
5. Particulates (also known as dust and aerosol emissions)	A measure of particle emissions and precursors to secondary particles, such as SO ₂ and NO _x , from sources like fossil fuel combustion, wood burning, and road and field dust. Particles cause adverse effects on human health, including respiratory diseases and increased global mortality rates.
6. Ozone Depletion	A measure of air emissions contributing to the destruction of the stratospheric ozone layer (i.e., the ozone hole). Ozone depletion leads to higher levels of UVB rays reaching the Earth's surface, producing harmful effects on humans and plants.

This study will focus on how to consider the carbon footprint in the asset life cycle cost (LCC) calculation, which will be called Green-LCC or G-LCC. It refers to the total amount of greenhouse gases produced directly and indirectly supporting human activities, usually expressed in equivalent tons of carbon dioxide (Navarro et al., 2021). The carbon footprint of an asset is calculated throughout its life cycle, from the extraction of raw materials, manufacturing, distribution, use, and disposal (ISO 14064-1:2018). This includes the emissions from the energy used in each of these stages. For instance, the carbon footprint of an asset considers the CO₂ emissions from the energy used in its production, transportation, installation, and commissioning (preparatory phase), but also during the operation and maintenance throughout its useful life cycle, from acquisition to the asset dismantling. The LCC analysis is essential for comprehending the costs associated with an asset over its entire lifespan (Crespo et al., 2018). The LCC considers various factors, including reliability analyses, and provides benefits such as enhanced cost visibility, analysis of business function interrelationships, and accurate profit estimations. The application of LCC techniques allows organizations to efficiently select their physical assets with a lower level of uncertainty. The traditional life cycle cost can be expressed in the following formula (Eq. (1)):

$$LCC_{Ownership} = \sum_{i=1}^T [Ownership Cost]_i = IC + OC + PMC + CMC + MMC - RV \quad (1)$$

Where:

- LCC: Life cycle costs (in this regards, the total ownership cost).
- T: expected useful life (in years).
- IC: Acquisition and installation costs.
- OC: Operation costs.
- PMC: Preventive maintenance costs (planned tasks).
- CMC: Corrective maintenance costs (due to failures, costs produced by the effects of low reliability)
- MMC: Major – special maintenance Costs (e.g. overhauls).
- RV: Remaining Value (or –[Disposal Cost])

Considering the carbon footprint in the asset LCC means value the cost of any possible carbon emissions. This is done by assigning a cost to the carbon emissions produced in each stage of the asset's life cycle. An additional cost is considered together with the other terms of the LCC analysis. A high carbon footprint can lead to higher costs due to penalties or potential carbon

taxes. Furthermore, assets with a high carbon footprint may have a shorter lifespan due to stricter environmental regulations, which can also increase the life cycle cost. Therefore, considering the carbon footprint in the asset LCC is important for the environmental and financial sustainability of the asset. However, monetizing the costs of CO₂ emissions is a very complex problem (Arendt et al., 2020; Hassan et al., 2021; Trovato et al., 2020) because it depends on many factors; for example, in the European Union, some large industries are subject to the emissions rights regime, but in other sectors, they are not (Stergiou & Kounetash, 2021). This study aims to approach calculating the cost of carbon emissions by integrating them into the LCC. This is intended to ensure that by using these sustainable practices, environmental standards are not compromised. This model could be used for digitization. To do this, it would be necessary to define the structure of the input data, the process of incorporation into the proposed formulation, and the extraction of the values of the total life cycle cost automatically. By analyzing this data, companies can make investment strategies for these assets. To simplify, the research questions are as follows: (i) What formula should be considered to include the carbon footprint in the LCC analysis? (ii) What would the LCC implementation process be like, taking advantage of the advantages of digitalization? This study is intended to promote that companies can reduce overall costs and increase profits by adopting a green approach. This will enable them to differentiate themselves from rivals and meet environmental goals.

2. Materials and Methodology

2.1. Proposed approach

ISO 14064-1:2018 is an international standard that guides the quantification and reporting of greenhouse gas emissions and removals at the organizational level. The standard includes requirements for designing, developing, managing, reporting, and verifying an organization's GHG inventory. Applying this standard to the asset LCC is a way to integrate the quantification and reporting of GHG emissions into the G-LCC analysis. This can be done by assigning a cost to the carbon emissions produced in each stage of the asset's life cycle, according to the guidelines provided by ISO 14064-1:2018, and adding to the other costs in the G-LCC analysis. Furthermore, the mentioned standard can also be used to identify opportunities for reducing GHG emissions and thus potentially reducing the G-LCC of the asset. For example, the standard can be used to identify energy-efficient practices or technologies that can be implemented to reduce the energy used and the carbon emissions of the asset. In addition, it can also be used to enhance the credibility and transparency of the G-LCC analysis. The standard provides guidelines for verifying GHG inventories, which can be used to ensure that the carbon emissions and their associated costs are accurately reported in the LCC analysis.

$$G - LCC^*_{ownership} = \sum_{t=1}^T [IC + OC + PMC + CMC + MMC - RV + \sum_{j=1}^{Life\ Cycle\ Stages} (Carbon\ Cost_j)]_i \quad (2)$$

A basic formula to consider the carbon footprint in the LCC expression can be represented as follows (Eq. (2)). (Crespo et Al., 2018).

The following seven steps model is proposed to consider digitalization within LCC and carbon footprint. This proposal has been considered cyclical to include any cases, such as changes in the operational context, analysis of new assets, or modifications to the business model within asset management.:

1. *Identify the Asset:* Identify the asset and those conditions or aspects that will be provided in addition. This could include maintenance tasks, energy-efficient needs, or other value-added uses.
2. *Identification and Monitoring of data:* Define the data necessary for the characterization of costs and determine the devices for its capture during the O&M of the asset.
3. *Calculate the Life Cycle Cost:* Calculate the life cycle cost of the asset, including the acquisition cost, operation cost, maintenance and repair cost, and disposal cost (Crespo et al., 2018).
4. *Calculate the Carbon Footprint Cost (CFC):* Calculate the cost associated with the carbon emissions produced in each asset life cycle stage. This can be done by multiplying the total amount of carbon emissions (in tons of CO₂ equivalent) by the cost per ton of CO₂ equivalent.
5. *Integrate the Costs:* Add the LCC and the CFC to get the asset G-LCC.
6. *Identify Opportunities for Cost and Carbon Reduction:* Identify opportunities for reducing the life cycle cost and the carbon footprint of the asset. This could include implementing energy-efficient practices, extending the asset's useful life, and enhancing the efficiency of the asset.
7. *Compare with traditional ownership cost:* It may facilitate decisions on sustainability and determine more affordable and profitable options for the company.

One way to digitize the carbon footprint would be designing a digital twin of the asset. For this purpose, it is necessary to break down the asset into components until the level of the element where carbon emissions take place. These components must be identified, technically located, and equipped with attributes that contain the values of carbon emissions. This task requires designing three types of codes: identity codes, technical location codes, and attribute codes for each asset or element. These three types of codes together constitute an inheritable data structure among elements of different levels, allowing the accounting of emissions throughout the established hierarchical structure. This data structure ensures the correct allocation of carbon emissions to each factor that makes up the formula for calculating the G-LCC.

2.2. Justification of the proposal

Digitalization can play a significant role in calculating carbon footprint and the asset life cycle cost. Digital technologies can help in accurately tracking and quantifying carbon emissions produced in each stage of the asset's life cycle (European Commission, 2021). For instance, sensors and Internet of Things (IoT) devices can be used to monitor the energy use of the asset in real-time, which can then be used to calculate carbon emissions. Similarly, software tools can be used to analyze these data and provide insights into the carbon footprint of the asset. Moreover, data analytics can be used to identify energy-efficient practices or technologies that can be implemented to reduce energy use and the carbon emissions of the asset (European Commission, 2021). The integration of digital technologies into LCC and CFC analysis in G-LCC can provide several key benefits that justify its adoption (Table 2):

Table 2. Summary of advantages

No.	Advantage	Summary
1	Enhanced Data Accuracy and Level of Detail	It provides a way to collect high-resolution data efficiently through the lifecycle of an asset, which is critical in calculating CO ₂ emissions. Precision helps to find out where it should reduce emissions and costs.
2	Real-Time Monitoring and Control	Through Industry 4.0 and IoT technology, continuous feedback is obtained that optimizes energy used and reduces emissions. Sensors for assets are controlled to ensure monitoring throughout the time.
3	Predictive Analytics for Proactive Decision-Making	To prevent the cost that would come from repairs and reduce emissions of greenhouse gases, assets are analyzed through predictive techniques.

4	Streamlined Reporting and Compliance	Through digitalization, one can automate data collection and simplify reporting. Hence, it simplifies the monitoring of carbon-based activities.
5	Life Cycle Optimization	It allows us to get a broader view of economic and environmental aspects using tools to identify better ways to improve.
6	Support for Circular Economy Principles	The digital context helps circular economies and reduces waste with better resource management.
7	Decision Support Systems	It is responsible for making smart plans to reduce carbon emissions and costs by interpreting complicated datasets.
8	Standardization and Benchmarking	Digital devices are a great source of data through which the amount of carbon and resources used can be assessed.
9	Enhanced Stakeholder Engagement	Digital platforms allow and improve effective communication between different shareholders to design innovative plans to reduce carbon costs and emissions.
10	Agility and Responsiveness	Digitalization provides agility to respond quickly to new information, regulations, or market demands, crucial for maintaining competitive advantage and compliance.

Digitalization serves more than just reporting and monitoring needs. It is a resource for applying the knowledge gained to effect real change. Furthermore, digitalization can also enhance the transparency and credibility of the carbon footprint and life cycle cost calculations. Using digital technologies can ensure that data are accurately recorded and reported, which can enhance the trust in the calculations. Additionally, digitalization can facilitate the integration of carbon footprint into life cycle cost analysis, as these tools can be easily used to assign a cost to carbon emissions and integrate that cost into life cycle cost analysis. of life.

3. Conclusions

This study highlights the link between effective asset management, contribution to carbon footprint reduction, and environmental sustainability. The carbon footprint integration into traditional life cycle cost analysis provides organizations with a sustainable perspective on overall costs associated with the lifetime of an asset. The proposed formula and digitalization model, guided by ISO 14064-1: 2018, offer realistic channels for cost incorporation into G-LCC analyses. Digitalization becomes a key enabler in this process and provides benefits such as increased data reliability, real-time monitoring capabilities focusing on predictive analytics, and simplified reporting options. The idea of a digital twin for greater accuracy in measuring the carbon footprint increases transparency and efficiency for environmental impact studies. Economic benefits associated with this dual approach significantly go beyond environmental concerns, as it allows for identifying opportunities to reduce costs while improving results. If organizations pursue environmental objectives and position themselves differently from their competitors, a green stance supported by digital technologies becomes strategic. This study encourages ecological practices to create a healthier environment and to comply with good cost control practices. The proposed approaches and digitalization strategies can be considered a practical instrument for companies trying to reconcile their financial results success and environmental responsibility.

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09.00 10.00	WELCOME - OPENING ADRESSES			
10.00 10.45	PLENARY SESSION ISABEL PARDO DE VERA. POLÍTICAS DE TRANSPORTE: PENSAMIENTO CATEDRAL Y TECNOLOGÍA CONTRA EL CORTOPLACISMO			
10.45 11.15	COFFEE BREAK			
11.15 12.45	RAIL SESSION Digitalization in manufacturing and O&M of railway rolling stock	CIBERSECURITY SESSION Decentralized cybersecurity of critical engineering assets	Strategy & Planning	Performance and Condition of Physical Assets 1
12.45 14.15	LUNCH			
14.15 15.00	PLENARY SESSION CRISTIANO MARTINCIGH, COPPERLEAF. OPTIMISED ASSET INVESTMENT PLANNING WITH COPPERLEAF - MAKING THE RIGHT DECISIONS AT THE RIGHT TIME TO MAXIMISE VALUE AND MEET STRATEGIC GOALS			
15.00 16.30	RAIL SESSION Digital Transformation in Rail Infrastructure	DIGITALIZATION AND RISK MANAGEMENT SESSION Digitalization and Risk Management of Critical Engineering Assets	Life Cycle Management 1	Performance and Condition of Physical Assets 2
16.30 17.00	COFFEE BREAK			
17.00 18.30	CASE STUDIES ON ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT	HYDROGEN SESSION Technical and Energetic Challenges in the Transition from Natural gas to Hydrogen	Life Cycle Management 2	SPECIAL SESSION Digital IAMS for integral LCM
20.00	WELCOME COCKTAIL			

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09.00 09.45	PLENARY SESSION ABEL GOMES. APPLUS. DIGITALIZACIÓN DE LA RED DE CARRETERAS DE UNA REGIÓN EN ESPAÑA. LECCIONES APRENDIDAS PARA EL SOPORTE DE LA GESTIÓN DE LA INFRAESTRUCTURA			
09.45 10.30	PLENARY SESSION NUNO MEDEIROS. EPAL. A NEUTRALIDADE CARBÓNICA, A TRANSFORMAÇÃO DIGITAL E A SUSTENTABILIDADE DA CADEIA DE VALOR DO NEGÓCIO COMO CATALISADORES DE UMA VISÃO (AINDA) MAIS HOLÍSTICA DA GESTÃO ESTRATÉGICA DE ATIVOS DO CICLO URBANO DA ÁGUAEPAL.			
10.30 11.00	COFFEE BREAK			
11.00 12.30	APMI-AEM SESSION Maintenance and Asset Management. Future and Trends in the Iberian Region	CIRCULAR ECONOMY SESSION BIOCHAR Applications and Circular Economy	Data Asset and Digital Transformation 1	WORKSHOP The Copperleaf optimization game
12.30 14.00	LUNCH			
14.00 14.45	PLENARY SESSION. TIAGO FERNANDES, ALFONSO LACERDA. EVORA GOLD PARTNER SAP. CONNECT THE DOTS TO ACHIEVE ASSET MANAGEMENT EXCELLENCE- THE IMPORTANCE OF ENTERPRISE ASSET MANAGEMENT IN THE DIGITAL WORLD.			
14.45 16.15	APMI-AEM SESSION People in Maintenance and Asset management in the Iberian Region	LOCAL GOVERNMENT SESSION Improving asset management in local governments	Management Systems and Standards 1	Sustainability 1
16.15 16.45	COFFEE BREAK			
16.45 18.15	CASE STUDIES ON ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT	LOCAL GOVERNMENT SESSION Building sustainable communities with asset management	Data Asset and Digital Transformation 2	Management Systems and Standards 2
20.00	GALA DINNER			

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5th OF JULY 2024 DRAFT PROGRAM

09.00 09.45	PLENARY SESSION. JOE AMADI-ECHENDU , DAVID MCKEON,, EDMEA ADELL, ALAN WILSON. EXPLORING FUTURE PERSPECTIVES IN ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT: INSIGHTS FROM EMINENT LEADERS .			
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11.15 11.45	COFFEE BREAK			
11.45 13.15	ORGANIZATION AND PEOPLE SESSION Intelligent Asset Management : People, Processes and Technology as enablers for ISO 55001 Certification	Data Asset and Digital Transformation	Sustainability 3	People & Competence
13.15 14.00	CLOSING CEREMONY			
14.00	LUNCH			

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10.00 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION. ID 44. POLÍTICAS DE TRANSPORTE PENSAMIENTO CATEDRAL Y TECNOLOGÍA CONTRA EL CORTOPLACISMO. ISABEL PARDO DE VERA.
10.45	COFFEE BREAK POWERED BY CAF
11.15 AUDITORIUM I	RAIL SESSION. ID 119. DIGITALIZATION IN MANUFACTURING AND O&M OF RAILWAY ROLLING STOCK.
	<i>Chair: Luis Andrade Ferreira. Centro de Competências Ferroviário Javier de la Cruz, CAF José Antonio Marcos. TALGO Alexandra Prates. CP Metropolitano de Lisboa</i>
11.15 AUDITORIUM III	CYBERSECURITY SESSION. ID 58. NAORIS PROTOCOL: WORLD'S FIRST DECENTRALIZED CYBERSECURITY MESH ARCHITECTURE. DAVID CARVALHO
	ID 116. BRIDGING THE GAP: WEB 3.0 AND CYBER-PHYSICAL INTEGRATION IN ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT
	<i>Chair: João Santos. Naoris David Carvalho. Naoris Miguel Oliveira. University of Aveiro Luis Ramalhão Santos. OET Jorge Liça. OE Carlos Ribeiro. Ex Director CSI</i>
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ID 129	LA BUENA VIDA DE LAS INFRAESTRUCTURAS. SERGIO VÁZQUEZ TORRÓN. INECO
ID 126	DIGITALIZACIÓN Y GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS FERROVIARIOS. BEGOÑA MARTÍN Y JOÃO DIONISIO. COMSA
ID 131	PROJETO TRANSVERSAL DE GESTÃO DE ATIVOS PARA O MATERIAL CIRCULANTE E OFICINAS FERROVIÁRIAS - UMA ABORDAGEM PRÁTICA PARA A MELHORIA DOS PROCESSOS E DA PRODUTIVIDADE. SILVIA FERREIRA Y MIGUEL RODRIGUES. CP
17.00 AUDITORIUM III	HYDROGEN SESSION. ID 99. TECHNICAL AND ENERGETIC CHALLENGES IN THE TRANSITION FROM NATURAL GAS TO HYDROGEN. ENAGAS
	Chair: Javier Serra. Enagas
17.00 ROOM 2	LIFE CYCLE MANAGEMENT. SESSION 2. ESTEFANÍA CERVANTES.
ID 51	ON-LINE CONDITION MONITORING OF ELECTRIC MOTOR DRIVES BASED ON ELECTRICAL ANALYSIS – SUCCESS CASE STUDIES IN INDUSTRY. JORGE ESTIMA
ID 55	POTENTIAL IMPACTS OF IMPLEMENTING CIRCULAR ECONOMY PRACTICES IN THE NIGERIAN FOREST PRODUCTS INDUSTRY: A SOCIAL LIFECYCLE ANALYSIS APPROACH. ISRAEL DUNMADE
ID 59	APLICACIÓN DE AUDITORÍA DE MANTENIMIENTO Y MODELO DE GESTIÓN DE MANTENIMIENTO A EMPRESA MANUFACTURERA DE PRODUCTOS COSMÉTICOS. CARLOS PARRA
ID 61	FACTORES DE SUCESSO E BLOQUEIO NO PLANEAMENTO E GESTÃO DAS INFRAESTRUTURAS URBANAS DE SUBSOLO. ANDRÉ SALVADOR
ID 104	AUDITORIA TÉCNICA NA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS INDUSTRIAIS: UMA ABORDAGEM SUSTENTÁVEL NA PERSPETIVA DA OTIMIZAÇÃO DO CICLO DE VIDA ÚTIL. CLÁUDIA ROCHA

3rd of July Draft Programme

17.00 ROOM 5	SPECIAL SESSION. DIGITAL INTELLIGENT ASSET MANAGEMENT SOLUTIONS (IAMS) FOR INTEGRAL ASSET LIFECYCLE MANAGEMENT. CHAIR ADOLFO CRESPO DEL CASTILLO.
ID 21	EXPLORING THE CARBON FOOTPRINT'S EFFECT ON LIFE CYCLE COSTS WITH DIGITALIZATION'S SUPPORT. VICENTE GONZÁLEZ-PRIDA
ID 24	EARLY FAILURE DETECTION IN SECONDARY CRYOGENIC PUMPS THROUGH MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES IN THE CONTEXT OF INDUSTRY 4.0. SONIA LIÑAN
ID 45	DYNAMIC FLEET MAINTENANCE MANAGEMENT: INTEGRATING PREVENTIVE MAINTENANCE AND PREDICTIVE CBM WITH OPERATION SCHEDULING. ADOLFO CRESPO DEL CASTILLO
ID 46	FRAMEWORK FOR ASSET DIGITALIZATION: A HOLISTIC APPROACH FOR ENHANCED MANAGEMENT AND RELIABILITY IN THE DIGITAL ERA. EDUARDO CANDÓN
ID 47	STRATEGIC INTEGRATION OF DIGITAL INTELLIGENCE: TRANSFORMING ASSET MANAGEMENT ACROSS THE LIFECYCLE FOR INFORMED DECISION-MAKING. ADOLFO CRESPO MÁRQUEZ
ID 80	DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF MAINTENANCE AND ASSET MANAGEMENT. GFM&AM'S PROJECT 25DX INSIGHTS. ADOLFO CRESPO MÁRQUEZ
20.00	WELCOME COCKTAIL OCEANÁRIO

4th of July Draft Programme

09.00 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION. ID 123. DIGITALIZACIÓN DE LA RED DE CARRETERAS DE UNA REGIÓN EN ESPAÑA. LECCIONES APRENDIDAS PARA EL SOPORTE DE LA GESTIÓN DE INFRAESTRUCTURAS. ABEL GOMES. APPLUS.
09.45 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION. ID 134. A NEUTRALIDADE CARBÓNICA, A TRANSFORMAÇÃO DIGITAL E A SUSTENTABILIDADE DA CADEIA DE VALOR DO NEGÓCIO COMO CATALISADORES DE UMA VISÃO (AINDA) MAIS HOLÍSTICA DA GESTÃO ESTRATÉGICA DE ATIVOS DO CICLO URBANO DA ÁGUA. NUNO MEDEIROS. EPAL.
10.30	COFFEE BREAK POWERED BY AYESA
11.00 AUDITORIUM I	APMI-AEM SESSION. ID 121 MAINTENANCE AND ASSET MANAGEMENT: FUTURE AND TRENDS IN THE IBERO-AMERICAN SPACE <i>Chair: Adolfo Crespo Márquez Claudio Rodríguez. AEM Diogo Brito. APMI Marcela Scalco. ABRAMAN</i>
	ID 122. DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN MAINTENANCE AND ASSET MANAGEMENT IN THE IBERIAN REGION <i>Chair: Adolfo Crespo Márquez José Antonio Marcos. TALGO Pedro Conceição (SONAE ARAUCO) Hugo Lebre (INFRASPEAK) Ignacio Moratalla Aguirre (AYESA)</i>
11.00 AUDITORIUM III	CIRCULAR ECONOMY SESSION. ID 95: BIOCHAR APPLICATIONS AND CIRCULAR ECONOMY. ATIV <i>Chair: Cátia Neves. ATIV - Mota ENGIL</i>
11.00 ROOM 2	DATA ASSET & DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION. SESSION 1. ANTONIO GUILLÉN LÓPEZ.
ID 11	THE IMPACT OF BLOCKCHAIN TECHNOLOGY FOR SUSTAINABLE ASSET MAINTENANCE IN TELECOMS DOMAIN IN EMERGING MARKETS. CHARLES OKEYIA
ID 13	CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS FOR INCREASING PRODUCTIVITY AND OVERCOMING THE DIGITALIZATION DEFICIT OF THE AECO INDUSTRY. SEYED REZVANJ
ID 89	IMPLANTAÇÃO DE SISTEMA DE GESTÃO DE ATIVOS NA EMBASA: INTEGRAÇÃO DE SISTEMAS DE INFORMAÇÃO. RINALDO CAMURUGY
ID 33	MODELAÇÃO PARAMÉTRICA DE ANOMALIAS EM TÚNEIS FERROVIÁRIOS. ANA ROCHA
ID 106	A VALUE-BASED DECISION-MAKING PROCESS FOR DIGITAL TWINNING OPPORTUNITIES IN RAIL AND ROAD INFRASTRUCTURE ASSET MANAGEMENT. JOÃO VIEIRA

ID 3	DIGITALIZATION STRATEGY FOR ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT IN THE CONTEXT OF INDUSTRY'S NET-ZERO TRANSITION. <i>ÁLVARO RODRÍGUEZ PRIETO</i>
11.00 AUDITORIUM II	WORKSHOP. ID 5. THE COPPERLEAF OPTIMIZATION GAME. CRISTIANO MARTINCIGH.
12.30	LUNCH RESTAURANTE D' BACALHAU
14.00 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION. ID 130. CONNECT THE DOTS TO ACHIEVE ASSET MANAGEMENT EXCELLENCE – THE IMPORTANCE OF ENTERPRISE ASSET MANAGEMENT IN A DIGITAL WORLD. TIAGO FERNANDES, SAP & ALFONSO LACERDA, EVORA.
14.45 AUDITORIUM I	APMI-AEM SESSION. ID 124. PEOPLE IN MAINTENANCE AND ASSET MANAGEMENT IN THE IBERIAN REGION .
	<i>Chair: Daniel Gaspar José Luis Bernal. MASA Álvaro Rodríguez Prieto. UNED Paulo Peixoto (ATEC) Mário Aguiam (ISQ)</i>
14.45 AUDITORIUM III	LOCAL GOVERNMENT SESSION. ID 96. IMPROVING ASSET MANAGEMENT IN LOCAL GOVERNMENTS. CHAIR MIGUEL ALMEIDA.
14.45 ROOM 2	MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS AND STANDARDS. SESSION 1. CHAIR RITA BRITO.
ID 19	SISTEMA DE GESTÃO DE ATIVOS NA MANUTENÇÃO DE PAVIMENTOS RODOVIÁRIOS. <i>JOSÉ VAZ</i>
ID 27	LOS SISTEMAS DE GETIÓN DE ACTIVOS DE CARRETERAS COMO HERRAMIENTAS PARA LA OPTIMIZACIÓN DE LOS PRESUPUESTOS DE CONSERVACIÓN. <i>ALBERTO MARTINEZ NAVARRO</i>
ID 83	GESTÃO DE ATIVOS APLICADA EMPRESAS DE SANEAMENTO: IMPLANTAÇÃO DE MODELO NA EMPRESA BAIANA DE ÁGUAS E SANEAMENTO (EMBASA). <i>ALISSON BRANDÃO</i>
ID 77	NEW VALUE PERSPECTIVE FOR SOCIAL PRICELESS ASSETS THROUGH DIGITAL TRANSFORMATIONS. <i>JOAQUÍN ORDIERES-MERÉ</i>
ID 78	DESAFIOS ATUAIS DA E-REDES NA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS TÉCNICOS. <i>MIGUEL FREITAS</i>
14.45 ROOM 5	SUSTAINABILITY. SESSION 1. CHAIR: ANA SILVA.
ID 56	AVALIAÇÃO EX-ANTE DA PRODUÇÃO DE MISTURAS BETUMINOSAS CONSIDERANDO TRÊS CENÁRIOS DE PRODUÇÃO ALTERNATIVOS. <i>ANA ROCHA</i>

ID 71	THE SYNERGY BETWEEN LEAN PHILOSOPHY AND VALUE ENGINEERING FOR NEW PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT. <i>ANDRÉ GUIMARÃES</i>
ID 72	SOLUÇÃO CONJUGADA DE CONSTRUÇÃO TRADICIONAL E TECNOLOGIA MODULAR PARA BAIROS INFORMAIS SUSTENTÁVEIS EM CABO VERDE. <i>FELISBERTO CORTES</i>
ID 75	"BOTICAR" PROJECT – THE FIRST STEPS TOWARDS DECARBONISATION IN PORTUGAL
ID 90	IMPLANTAÇÃO DA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS NO SISTEMA DE ABASTECIMENTO DE ÁGUA E ESGOTAMENTO SANITÁRIO DE BARRA DE POJUCA NA EMBASA – EMPRESA BAIANA DE ÁGUAS E SANEAMENTO. <i>RINALDO CAMURUGY</i>
16.15	COFFEE BREAK
16.45 AUDITORIUM I	CASE STUDIES ON ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT. CHAIR JOAQUÍN ORDIERES
	GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS FERROVIARIOS. TALGO
ID 128	IMPORTANCIA DEL FACTOR HUMANO EN LA APLICACIÓN DE LA INGENIERÍA DEL MANTENIMIENTO EN LA GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS. <i>JOSÉ LUIS BERNAL. MASA</i>
ID 115	UN ENFOQUE UNIFICADO DE LA GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS MEDIANTE SAP Y BIM EN AT/MT/BT ELÉCTRICA. <i>IGNACIO MORATALLA AGUIRRE. AYESA</i>
16.45 AUDITORIUM III	LOCAL GOVERNMENT SESSION. ID 97. BUILDING SUSTAINABLE COMMUNITIES WITH ASSET MANAGEMENT. CHAIR MIGUEL ALMEIDA.
16.45 ROOM 2	DATA ASSETS & DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION. SESSION 2. CHAIR: VICENTE GONZÁLEZ PRIDA.
ID 15	INDUSTRIAL IOT AND 3D DIGITAL TWIN FOR REAL TIME-EVERGREENING OF ENGINEERING ASSETS SUBJECTED TO CORROSION UNDER INSULATION. <i>ALVARO RODRÍGUEZ-PRIETO</i>
ID 26	UNA EFICAZ GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS DE REDES DE CARRETERAS A PARTIR DE GEMELOS DIGITALES. <i>ALBERTO MARTINEZ NAVARRO</i>
ID 70	OVERVIEW OF THE USE OF DATA ASSETS IN THE CONTEXT OF PORTUGUESE COMPANIES: COMPARISON BETWEEN SMES AND LARGE COMPANIES. <i>ANDRÉ GUIMARÃES</i>
ID 73	MODIFICAÇÃO DO MÉTODO DELPHI PARA APLICAÇÃO NUM QUESTIONÁRIO SOBRE A TRANSFORMAÇÃO DIGITAL NA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS. <i>SAMUEL MESSIAS</i>
ID 103	NDE & SENSING SOLUTIONS FOR PIPELINE STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING. <i>GABRIEL DINIS</i>
ID 112	DIGITALIZING BUILDING MAINTENANCE: BIM-POWERED ASSET MANAGEMENT SOLUTIONS. <i>ANA SILVA</i>

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16.45 ROOM 5	MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS AND STANDARDS. SESSION 2. FILIPA SALVADO.
ID 16	COLLECTIVE USE BUILDINGS ASSET MANAGEMENT BASED ON TECHNICAL AND ESSENTIAL REQUIREMENTS. <i>MARIA JOÃO FALCÃO</i>
ID 35	IMPLEMENTATION PROCESS OF AN ISO 55001 CERTIFIED ASSET MANAGEMENT MODEL IN THE NATURAL GAS INDUSTRY. <i>JAVIER SERRA</i>
ID 41	IMPLEMENTACIÓN DE UN PLAN DE GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS SEGÚN LA NORMA ISO 55001 EN LA CENTRAL DE GENERACIÓN ELÉCTRICA COLMITO.
ID 63	A EVOLUÇÃO E PERSPETIVAS DA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS: UM MODELO ABRANGENTE E INTEGRADO DE GESTÃO DE ATIVOS INDUSTRIAIS. <i>JOAQUIM CABRAL MARTINS</i>
ID 82	CERTIFICAÇÃO ISO 55001 NA E-REDES – UMA AVALIAÇÃO APÓS DOIS ANOS. <i>CRISTINA CARVALHO</i>
ID 110	IMPORTÂNCIA DO ALINHAMENTO DAS FUNÇÕES ORGANIZACIONAIS E DA ESTRUTURAÇÃO DOS ATIVOS NA TOMADA DE DECISÃO SOBRE INVESTIMENTOS NO SETOR DA ÁGUA. <i>JAIME GABRIEL SILVA</i>
20.00	GALA DINNER KAIS RESTAURANTE

5th of July Draft Programme

09.00 AUDITORIUM I	PLENARY SESSION ID 113. EXPLORING FUTURE PERSPECTIVES IN ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT: INSIGHTS FROM EMINENT LEADERS.
	Chair: Adolfo Crespo Márquez David Mckewon. Vicepresidente honorario del Instituto de Gestión de Activos Joe Amadi Echendu. Presidente de la Junta Directiva de la Sociedad Internacional de Gestión de Activos de Ingeniería Edmea Adell. Presidente de IFRAMI y miembro de ISO/TC 251 Asset Management Alan Wilson. Representante del Comité de Gestión de Activos de la Federación Europea de Sociedades Nacionales de Mantenimiento
09.45 AUDITORIUM I	CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE SESSION. ID 135. THE ROLE OF ASSET MANAGEMENT IN THE RESILIENCE OF CRITICAL INFRASTRUCTURE. EPAL
	Chair: Ana Margarida Luís. AdP Valor Miguel Freitas. E-REDES Vanessa Martins. EPAL Javier Serra. ENAGÁS Infraestructuras de Portugal
09.45 AUDITORIUM III	ENTREPRENEURSHIP COMPETITION. CHAIR EDUARDO LEITE
ID 8	EUROPEAN ACTION TOWARDS MORE ENTREPRENEURIAL AND INNOVATIVE UNIVERSITIES. <i>NUNO ALMEIDA</i>
ID 74	ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION: FAILURE PREVENTION AS A PILLAR FOR SUCESS. <i>EDUARDO LEITE</i>
ID 20	NETOBRA. A TECHNOLOGICAL ADVANCEMENT FOR URBAN RESILIENCE IN THE AECO SECTOR. <i>SEYED REZVANI</i>
ID 117	SPOTLITE. RISK MONITORING FROM SPACE. <i>NUNO DURO</i>
ID 127	DIPROTOS. SISTEMA DE MONITORIZAÇÃO E VIGILÂNCIA DOS ATIVOS: PARQUES PÚBLICOS INFANTIS E DE LAZER. <i>ANTÓNIO ROQUE</i>
ID 94	BCIRCLE. PROJECTO "BOTICHAR". UMA UNIDADE DE PRODUÇÃO EFICIENTE E ESCALÁVEL. <i>DIEGO ARÁN</i>
ID 102	AECYCLE. SUSTAINABLE AND DIGITAL INNOVATIONS IN ENGINEERING ASSET MANAGEMENT. <i>MARCO PEDROSO</i>
ID 109	CASADOMO. HABITAÇÃO INOVADORA E SUSTENTÁVEL EM SUPERDOBE MODULAR PARA BAIROS INFORMAIS DA CIDADE DA PRAIA - CABO VERDE. <i>FELISBERTO CORTÉS</i>
09.45 ROOM 2	SUSTAINABILITY. SESSION 2. CHAIR ANA LUÍSA CABRITA
ID 114	SUSTAINABILITY AND OTHER OUTCOMES - THE VALUE OF A STRATEGIC ASSET MANAGEMENT APPROACH. <i>DAVID MCKEOWN</i>

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ID 31	A COMPARATIVE STUDY IN EUROPE TO MEASURE THE IMPACT OF GOVERNMENT POLICIES, INDUSTRY ON PUBLIC PERCEPTION OF RENEWABLE ENERGY. <i>KHULOUD KALTHOUM</i>
ID 17	PROTECTING AND REALIZING VALUE FROM POLLINATION ASSETS: BEEKEEPING OR ASSET MANAGEMENT APPLIED TO NATURAL ASSETS?. <i>AZUCENA MARQUES</i>
ID 52	CIRCULAR ECONOMY AND SUSTAINABILITY IN INDUSTRY 5.0 – A RESEARCH AGENDA
ID 54	A STUDY ON THE PERCEPTION AND AWARENESS OF CIRCULAR ECONOMY PRACTICES BY MANUFACTURING COMPANIES IN SANGO-OTA REGION, OGUN STATE NIGERIA. <i>ISRAEL DUNMADE</i>
ID 107	HARNESSING THE POWER OF BIOMIMICRY FOR SUSTAINABLE INNOVATION IN PRODUCT DESIGN AND INDUSTRIAL DEVELOPMENT. <i>ARUNA M</i>
09.45 ROOM 5	RISK & RELIABILITY. CHAIR ANTONIO SÁNCHEZ.
ID 6	DATA MODEL TO DIGITIZATION OF CRITICALITY ANALYSIS IN RAILWAY SYSTEMS. <i>ÁNGEL MENA</i>
ID 1	APLICACIÓN DEL MODELO DE GESTIÓN DE MANTENIMIENTO (MGM) ALINEADO A UN PROCESO INTEGRAL DE GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS.CASO DE ESTUDIO: SINEA PERÚ, EMPRESA LÍDER EN LATINOAMÉRICA DEL SECTOR DE PRODUCCIÓN ENVASES RECICLADOS PARA BEBIDAS COMERCIALES (PET). <i>CARLOS PARRA</i>
ID 7	MATRIZ DE CRITICIDAD CUALITATIVA DE RIESGO (MCCR) APLICADA EN UNA LÍNEA DE PRODUCCIÓN DE ENVASES BIODEGRADABLES, <i>CARLOS PARRA</i>
ID 30	MODELO DE AVALIAÇÃO DO NÍVEL DO RISCO EM OBRAS DE CONTENÇÃO DA INFRAESTRUTURAS DE PORTUGAL: VISÃO GERAL DA ESTRUTURA E FUNCIONAMENTO. <i>JOÃO LUÍS AMADO</i>
ID 25	MODELO DE AVALIAÇÃO DO NÍVEL DO RISCO EM OBRAS DE CONTENÇÃO DA INFRAESTRUTURAS DE PORTUGAL: VALIDAÇÃO COM BASE EM DADOS REAIS. <i>JOÃO VINAGRE AMADO</i>
11.15	COFFEE BREAK
11.45 AUDITORIUM I	ORGANIZATION AND PEOPLE SESSION. ID 125. INTELLIGENT ASSET MANAGEMENT : PEOPLE , PROCESSES AND TECHNOLOGY AS ENABLERS FOR ISO 55001 CERTIFICATION. EVORA/SAP
	<i>Chair: Patrícia Franganito (Bureau Veritas) Tiago Fernandes (SAP EMEA) João Moura (Ernst & Young) Paula Branco (Metro do Porto) Ignacio Moratalla Aguirre (AYESA)</i>

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11.45 AUDITORIUM III	DATA ASSET & DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION. SESSION 3. CHAIR HUGO PATRÍCIO.
ID 37	GRADIENT BOOSTING CLASSIFIER-BASED APPROACH ON WASTEWATER NETWORK AGE PREDICTION FOR CRITICAL ASSETS IDENTIFICATION. <i>RICARDO FERREIRA</i>
ID 49	DIGITALIZAÇÃO E ANÁLISE FUNCIONAL INTEGRADA (AFI) NO PROCESSO DE TOMADA DE DECISÃO DA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS. <i>HUGO BRANQUINHO</i>
ID 50	INFODYNAMIC ANALYSIS OF DAMAGE DETECTION OF BRIDGES. <i>JORGE ALEXANDRE VIEIRA</i>
ID 57	MONITOREO DE LA SALUD ESTRUCTURAL MEDIANTE REALIDAD AUMENTADA Y VIRTUAL: UNA REVISIÓN INTEGRAL. <i>MATÍAS VALENZUELA</i>
ID 66	AVALIAÇÃO METODOLÓGICA DA APLICABILIDADE DA MONITORIZAÇÃO POR SATÉLITE NA GESTÃO DE ATIVOS RODOFERROVIÁRIOS. <i>JOÃO LUÍS AMADO</i>
11.45 ROOM 2	SUSTAINABILITY. SESSION 3. CHAIR JOSÉ CAMPOS E MATOS.
ID 32	GESTÃO DE ATIVOS DE ÁGUAS PLUVIAIS EM MEIO URBANO EM PORTUGAL – DESAFIOS PARA O SETOR. <i>RITA SALGADO BRITO</i>
ID 39	REALITY CAPTURE AND MODELLING FOR DIGITAL WATER MANAGEMENT: CASE STUDY OF WATER INFRASTRUCTURE ASSETS IN BRAZIL. <i>WAGNER CARVALHO</i>
ID 81	A IMPORTÂNCIA DA AVALIAÇÃO DA QUALIDADE NA GESTÃO E OTIMIZAÇÃO DE ATIVOS FOTOVOLTAICOS. <i>TERESA CANELAS</i>
ID 93	PATHWAYS TOWARDS NET-ZERO: MARKET DATA INSIGHTS ON PORTUGUESE REAL ESTATE ENERGY PERFORMANCE
ID 100	TRANSIÇÃO DIGITAL E INOVAÇÃO TECNOLÓGICA NO SETOR AECO - ESTRATÉGIAS INTEGRADAS PARA UM FUTURO SUSTENTÁVEL. <i>MARCO PEDROSO</i>
ID 105	COMO TORNAR UM AMS – ASSET MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OPERACIONAL E SUSTENTÁVEL. <i>EDMEA ADELL</i>
11.45 ROOM 5	PEOPLE AND COMPETENCE. CHAIR TICO MONTEIRO
ID 10	INNOVATION IN MAINTENANCE AND ASSET MANAGEMENT SKILLS TOWARDS DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION. <i>MARIA JOÃO FALCÃO SILVA</i>
ID 53	PROFICIÊNCIA DIGITAL DE ESTUDANTES DE ENGENHARIA: DESAFIOS E OPORTUNIDADES NO CENÁRIO EUROPEU. <i>CELIA DO CARMO LEANDRO</i>

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ID 60	FORTALECENDO A RESILIÊNCIA CLIMÁTICA EM SÃO TOMÉ E PRÍNCIPE: CAPACITAÇÃO DE JORNALISTAS PARA UMA COMUNICAÇÃO EFICAZ.
ID 87	PROPUESTA DE METODOLOGÍA DE GESTIÓN DEL CAMBIO COMO COMPLEMENTO AL MARCO DE REFERENCIA PARA UNA GESTIÓN DE ACTIVOS INTANGIBLES Y CONOCIMIENTO. VICENTE GONZÁLEZ PRIDA
ID 118	A IMPORTÂNCIA DA FORMAÇÃO PARA UM MELHOR DESEMPENHO NOS MÉTODOS E PLANEAMENTO DA MANUTENÇÃO DE ATIVOS. DÉRCIO DIAS
ID 2	CRITICAL ASSETS AND VALUE NETWORKS IN RESILIENT INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS IN THE EU OUTERMOST REGIONS. EDUARDO LEITE
13.15 AUDITORIUM I	CLOSING CEREMONY BEST PAPER DIGITALIZATION BEST PAPER SUSTAINABILITY ENTERPREUNERSHIP COMPETITION LIFETIME ACHIEVEMENT AWARD
13.45	LUNCH RESTAURANTE D' BACALHAU
